

Parents Reading Class Approach and Letter Sound Recognition of Kindergarten Pupils

Ivy J. Estabaya

Abstract. The purpose of this research study was to determine the effect of the parents' reading class approach on letter recognition among kindergarten pupils. The study was conducted at Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The study involved 60 kindergarten pupils, with 32 in section A as the controlled group and 28 in section B as the experimental group. Both sections were homogeneous in composition, with identical grades among learners. The study employed a non-random assignment of subjects, involving all learners from sections A and B as participants. Due to the pandemic, the experiment was conducted in a virtual classroom setting. A quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design, was utilized. T-tests and ETA square were employed to address research questions. Findings indicated a significant effect of the parents' reading class approach on letter recognition among kindergarten pupils. It is recommended that teachers of kindergarten pupils adopt the parents' reading class approach as a strategy to enhance letter sound recognition. School administrators are encouraged to promote this approach among their stakeholders to significantly improve letter recognition skills among kindergarten pupils.

KEY WORDS

1. parents reading class approach 2. letter recognition

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1. The Introduction

"Parents reading class approach" typically refers to educational programs or initiatives aimed at supporting parents in fostering their children's reading skills and literacy development. These classes often provide parents with strategies, resources, and guidance to engage their children in reading activities and promote a love for reading at home. These classes often involve interactive sessions where parents learn effective reading strategies and activities they can implement at home. Parents may be encouraged to model positive reading behaviors by reading aloud to their children and creating a reading-friendly environment at home. Parent reading classes may provide access to books, literacy materials, and online resources to support parents in facilitating reading activities with their children. Some programs may involve collaboration between schools and community organizations to offer parent reading classes as part of a broader effort to support children's literacy development LeFevre (2020). "Parent Involvement in Reading" (PIR) program. PIR focuses on enhancing children's reading abili-

ties by involving parents in reading activities at home. Studies have shown that parental involvement in reading positively impacts children's literacy skills and academic achievement (LeFevre, 2020). Letter sound recognition is a crucial early literacy skill that kindergarten pupils develop as they begin to learn to read. Kindergarten pupils typically start by learning the sounds associated with individual letters. They then progress to blending these sounds together to form simple words. Finally, they move on to more complex phonetic patterns and word structures. Letter sound recognition is closely linked to phonemic awareness, which is the ability to identify and manipulate individual sounds in spoken words. Kindergarten pupils engage in activities such as rhyming, segmenting, and blending sounds to develop phonemic awareness, which in turn supports letter sound recognition (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development 2021). Effective teaching of letter sound recognition often involves multisensory approaches that engage multiple senses, such as sight, hearing, and touch. Teachers may use alphabet blocks, letter cards, songs, and games to reinforce letter

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. Parents Reading Class Approach— Parent reading classes focus on shared reading activities where parents read aloud to their children, modeling fluent reading and introducing new vocabulary. Techniques such as asking open-ended questions, making predictions, and connecting texts to children's experiences enhance comprehension and critical thinking (Jzendoorn, 2020; Lonigan, 2020; Andrews, 2021).

These classes promote a literacy-rich home environment, encouraging regular reading, library visits, and book discussions, fostering a love for reading and continuous learning (LeFevre, 2020). Collaboration between parents and educators ensures alignment of home

sound associations. Letter sound recognition instruction is embedded within a rich literacy environment that includes exposure to a variety of print materials, such as books, charts, labels, and environmental print. Pupils learn to recognize letters and their sounds in context as they engage with these print materials (National Early Literacy Panel (2020). Teachers differentiate instruction based on individual pupil needs, providing additional support for pupils who struggle with letter sound recognition while challenging those who progress quickly. Small group instruction, one-on-one interventions, and peer tutoring are common strategies used to address diverse learning needs (Griffin, 2021). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, no study has been conducted to look for parents reading class approach and how it affects the kindergarten pupils letter sound recognition during this pandemic. Thus, the researcher finds it appropriate and timely to conduct this study to propose a plan of action on how teachers in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School further improve the letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils with the involvement of parents.

literacy practices with classroom instruction, enhancing continuity in learning (Epstein, 2020; Gaitan, 2022).

Engaging parents in reading classes is linked to improved academic outcomes, including better reading skills and a positive attitude towards reading (Epstein, 2021; Andrews, 2018; Newman, 2020). These classes build parents' confidence in supporting their children's literacy development and provide tailored resources based on children's needs (Desimone, 2020). However, parental involvement levels can vary, which might affect the effectiveness of this approach (Gest, 2022).

*1.1.2. Letter Sound Recognition—*Letter sound recognition, or phonemic awareness, is crucial in early literacy development. It involves

identifying and manipulating sounds associated with letters, aiding in word decoding and encoding. Effective instructional approaches include explicit phonics instruction, multisensory activities, and systematic practice, with tailored support for diverse student needs (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, 2023; Griffin, 2021).

This skill serves as a precursor to reading and literacy development, predicting later reading achievement and overall literacy skills (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, 2020). It supports phonemic awareness, essential for reading and spelling abilities, and fosters independence in writing (Ehri, 2022).

While letter sound recognition is fundamental, English spelling irregularities pose challenges. Despite this, it remains a strong predictor of early reading success and is positively correlated with spelling proficiency (Adams, 2021; Tunmer, 2020; Torgesen et al., 2020). Effective interventions targeting this skill significantly enhance literacy outcomes (Ehri, 2021).

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study sought to determine the Parents Reading Class Approach and Letter Sound Recognition of Kindergarten Pupils. Eventually, it also sought

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework—

This study is anchored on the theory of Vygotsky (2020), who emphasized the importance of social interactions and cultural context in learning. In the context of the Parents Reading Class Approach, parents and children engage in joint reading activities, creating opportunities for meaningful social interactions that support literacy development. This approach recognizes the cultural significance of family involvement in education and seeks to leverage it for children's learning. This is supported by Gillon (2022) who proposed the idea of Phonological Awareness Developmental Continuum. This theory outlines the sequential stages through which children typically progress in their development of phonological awareness, including letter sound recognition. Gillon's theory suggests that children initially develop an awareness of larger linguistic units, such as syllables and onset-rime units, before progressing to an understanding of individual phonemes (the smallest units of sound in language). Letter sound recognition falls within the phonemic awareness stage, where children become aware of the correspondence between letters and their associated sounds. Gillon emphasizes the importance of explicit instruction and practice in phonemic awareness to support children's literacy development. Through activities that focus on identifying and manipulating individual phonemes in spoken language, children gradually learn to associate specific phonemes with corresponding letters. This process is crucial for decoding written words during reading and encoding words during spelling.

to determine the magnitude of effect of Syntactic Skills on the reading knowledge acquisition of kindergarten pupils. Moreover, it aimed to answer the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the pre-test scores of the Kindergarten learners both from controlled and experimental groups?

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

- (2) What is the post test scores of the kindergarten learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference on the post test scores of the Kindergarten learners from controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of the Parents Reading Class Approach Methods and Letter Sound Recognition of Kindergarten Pupils?

1.5. *Null Hypothesis*—The null hypothesis in this study was tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. The Parents reading class approach has no effect on the letter recognition of the kindergarten pupils.

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to the following: DepEd. The Department of Education should know the results and findings of this study in order for them to create a policy that would consider parents reading class approach in teaching letter sound recognition to kindergarten pupils. Besides, the department will conduct an orientation for all school leaders on the conduct and benefits of the said approach.

School Heads. Being the manager in school, the school head needs to know the results and findings of this study for them to initiate a school-based program that would strengthen the implementation of parents reading class approach. Teachers. The teachers should have extended extra miles by utilizing the parents reading class approach to teach kindergarten pupils letter sound recognition. Learners can be guided further and learn faster if teachers will use the said approach. Future Researchers. The results and findings of this study will give insights to future researchers to the importance of using parents reading class approach in teaching letter sound recognition to kindergarten pupils.

2. Method

This chapter discussed the research method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

01	X	02
03	X	04

Note. 01 = Pretest of the experimental group; 02 = Posttest of the experimental group; 03 = Pretest of the controlled group; 04 = Posttest of the controlled group; ———= Non-random assignment of subjects; X = Treatment applied in the experimental group.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 kindergarten pupils – 32 were from section A which was the controlled group and 28 were from section B which were the experimental group. The composition

of these two sections were homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. Since it was pandemic time, the experiment was conducted in the virtual classroom.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A 32
2	Section B 28
Total	60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where the teacher gave module at the same meet the learners in face to face but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had met the learners with the permission of parents during face-to-face sessions for a follow up of what has been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance test consisted of a 25-item test

eventually determined the Letter Sound Recognition of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful in assessing the Letter Sound Recognition of the learners. On the hand, a posttest was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the Letter Sound Recognition of Kindergarten Pupils, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permis-

sion that this research study be conducted were sent to the Dr. Nelson C. Lopez, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division

Performance Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Fig. 2. Gantt Chart

of Davao Del Sur and to the School Principal of Sta Cruz Central Elementary School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert val-

idators, the researcher administered a pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commenced her experiment by using syllable strip in teaching decoding in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered a posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects was submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the Letter Sound Recognition of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. t-test for uncorre-

lated samples was used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and n groups. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of effect of Parents Reading Class Approach and Letter Sound Recognition of Kindergarten Pupils.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. Pre-Test Score of Learners—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade seven

learners. The controlled group got the mean of 57.68 or beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 60.96 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	32	14.42	57.68	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	28	15.24	60.96	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (2020) who cited that letter sound recognition is a critical foundational skill for kindergarten pupils as it serves as a precursor to reading and literacy development. Letter sound recognition is often considered a gateway skill to reading. It provides children with the ability to decode

words, which is essential for reading fluency and comprehension. Letter sound recognition during kindergarten has been found to predict later reading achievement and overall literacy skills. Parent reading classes often focus on creating a literacy-rich home environment by encouraging activities such as regular reading together, visits to the library, and discussions about books. These activities foster a love for reading and create opportunities for continuous learning outside of the classroom (LeFevre, 2020).

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	32	14.42	57.68	Beginning
Post-test	32	20.66	82.64	Developing
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	28	15.24	60.96	Beginning
Post-test	28	21.64	86.56	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade seven learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.66 or developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.64 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.4 from a mean rating of 15.24 to 21.64. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the

controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Gaitan (2022) who cited that parent involvement in reading classes helps create an enriched literacy environment at home, with parents incorporating reading activities, discussions, and book sharing into daily routines. This enriched environment provides additional opportunities for children to practice and reinforce their reading skills outside of school. Involving parents in reading classes allows educators to better understand the cultural and lin-

guistic backgrounds of their students. Parents can provide insights into their children’s unique needs, preferences, and strengths, enabling educators to tailor reading instruction to better meet individual student needs. The parent reading class approach offers several advantages in promoting literacy development in young children. Engaging parents in reading classes fosters active involvement in their children’s educa-

tion, which has been consistently linked to positive academic outcomes, including improved reading skills (Epstein, 2021). Parent reading classes strengthen the home-school connection by equipping parents with the knowledge and skills to support their children’s literacy development at home. This connection enhances the continuity of learning between school and home environments (LeFevre, 2021).

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	20	-5.37	.0436	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.37 with a p-value of .0436 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the kindergarten pupils. This implies that the used of parents reading class approach have contributed to the letter sound recognition which is revealed by the scores of the kindergarten pupils. This finding is in line with the statement of Andrews (2018) who cited that parents who participate in reading classes learn effective literacy strategies and techniques, which they can then model for their children. Children benefit from observing

their parents engage in reading activities and develop positive attitudes towards reading. Parent reading classes build parents’ confidence in their ability to support their children’s literacy development. As parents become more knowledgeable about literacy instruction, they feel empowered to play a more active role in their children’s learning Newman (2020). Reading classes for parents often provide tailored support and resources based on the specific needs of their children. Parents can receive guidance on selecting appropriate reading materials, implementing effective reading strategies, and addressing any challenges their children may encounter (Desimone, 2020).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Kindergarten Pupils

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.47	0.443	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of late afternoon program on the letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.443 which signifies large effect. This

implies that teachers should look for a strategy in enhancing students’ letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils. Developing letter sound recognition in kindergarten pupils is

a fundamental component of early literacy instruction. This skill serves as the foundation for reading and writing, critical abilities that influence academic success and lifelong learning. Letter sound recognition is a foundational skill that underpins various aspects of literacy development in kindergarten pupils. Its importance lies in its role as a precursor to reading, predictor of reading success, facilitator of phonemic awareness, potential for early intervention, support for vocabulary acquisition, and enhancement of writing skills (Ehri, 2022). Parents who support and reinforce the literacy instruction provided in school by extending learning opportunities at home contribute to improved reading achievement. Reading classes that pro-

vide parents with strategies for supporting their children's literacy development can lead to enhanced academic outcomes (Young, 2021). The benefits of a parent reading class approach are numerous, as it not only enhances the literacy skills of children but also fosters positive parent-child interactions and promotes a lifelong love of reading. Parent reading classes provide parents with strategies and techniques to support their children's literacy development at home. Research has shown that children whose parents participate in such classes demonstrate improved literacy skills, including better reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and phonemic awareness (LeFevre, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of parents reading class approach on the letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 kindergarten pupils— 32 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 28 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

This study revealed that the utilization of parents reading class approach has increased the letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the kindergarten pupils both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching

Proficiency. This means that there is a significant effect of the Parents reading approach and letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching kindergarten pupils should used parents reading

class approach as a strategy that would further develop the letter sound recognition. Developing letter sound recognition in kindergarten pupils is a critical aspect of early literacy instruction with far-reaching implications for academic and cognitive development. The school heads should promote the use of parents reading class approach that would further enhance the letter sound recognition of kindergarten pupils as it is revealed in the study that it is an essential skill that enables children to decode words, develop phonemic awareness, and build spelling and writing abilities. A school policy about the utilization of parents reading class approach can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using parents reading class approach as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of parents reading class approach as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

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